

METU in New European Research Area (*in Turkish*)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zela ÖZDEMİR

Research Coordination Office / Middle East Technical University

Moderator: Yelda Erden Topal

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, June 17, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/VGW36xfNTRbLCE9D7>

Moderation: Dr. Yelda Erden Topal

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 16 June 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 16 June 2022.

Abstract: In this session the speakers will discuss the evolution of European Research Area (ERA) to the new ERA in order to grasp its priorities as well as normative anchor points and locate METU within this ambitious programme. The aim of the European Research Area is to create a unified European research market for innovation and technology. Since its inception in 2000, the ERA has promoted EU research and innovation by facilitating the flow of experts and knowledge and by harmonizing national policies and research programmes. The EU is now modernised the ERA through Communication for 'A New ERA for Research and Innovation.' To further strengthen Europe's world-leading research, a strong ERA is essential and must be based on research excellence, international collaboration, openness, inclusiveness, and academic freedom.

Speakers:

Dr. Sara Banu AKKAŞ has B.Sc. (2001), M.Sc. (2003) and Ph.D. (2009) degrees from the Department of Biology, Middle East Technical University. Dr. Akkaş has gained major experience in project development; implementation and management by means of the various roles she has undertaken in several national (e.g. TÜBİTAK) and international (e.g. H2020, FP7, FP6 and Newton Fund) research projects throughout her research career. She worked as an "International Projects Expert" within an SME in ODTÜ Technopark between 2008-2010, and has been working in ODTÜ Research Coordination Office (RCO) since March 2010. She became

the coordinator of the Office of Sponsored Projects under the umbrella of RCO in February 2015 and now is the coordinator of RCI since November 2019. She was in the organising committee of the "Conference on Turkish Universities in the European Research Area (ERA)" held in Ankara, Turkey on October 8-9, 2015 and coordinated a Professional Development and Engagement Programme Project match funded by the British Council and ODTÜ under the Newton-

Katip Çelebi Fund developed within the context of the 2015 UK-Turkey Year of Science and Innovation. She has coordinated 2 H2020-MSCA-NIGHT projects and 3 Researchers' Night events (2016, 2017 and 2019). She is also the Head of the HRS4R Working Group of ODTÜ, which is the first university in Turkey to obtain the HR Excellence in Research Award. She values the vision to better align the core values of Turkish research universities with the EU HRS4R and is glad for the chance to contribute to the open, transparent, merit-based recruitment and equal opportunities literacy of Turkish research universities.

Dr. Zelal ÖZDEMİR received her doctoral degree in Area Studies at METU. She has post-graduate degrees from School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS) and London School of Economics (LSE) in International Relations and Sociology. Currently, she teaches at the interdisciplinary programmes of Middle Eastern Studies and Area Studies and works as a scientific project expert at the Research Coordination Office of METU. Her research interests include border studies, migration, gender politics and, civil society and social movements. She has been involved in many national and international projects (FP6, FP7, Horizon 2020) both in proposal writing and implementation phases. She is the member of the METU team responsible from ERA Priority 4: Gender Equality and Gender Mainstreaming in Research and aims to accelerate the efforts of Turkish and European stakeholders for integration of Turkish and European Research Areas coordinated by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey on behalf of the Ministry of Industry and Technology. She is also the PI of Horizon 2020 Project, 'Europe's Regional Partnership for Gender Equality in the Digital Age'- 'EQUALS-EU'. She has several publications in peer-reviewed journals including Political Geography.

About SolarTwins- TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Sustainable Energy and Climate Policies in the Light of Changing Global and Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAKTR: Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	S. Banu AKKAŞ, Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective

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